

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

this cetificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Саидмаматова Мохинур

СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ В МЕДИЦИНЕ

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

YANVAR/ 2023

